

Roadmap database

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ABSTRACT

This document presents the first deliverable from Task 6.1 “Roadmap for wider uptake of water-smart solutions”. The objective is to provide a structured and clear roadmap approach as part of the basis for developing the subsequent roadmap guide (D6.6). The document contains a clear definition of the roadmap steps: scoping, forecasting, backcasting, and transfer. A database with fields for all the required data that should be collected in the roadmapping steps is presented. The case studies in WIDER UPTAKE are summarised and discussed in relation to the state of the art for their solutions, what stage of implementation they are at, and what the focus of further development using the roadmap guide could be. Data for each case study acquired previously and relevant for the scoping step are presented and discussed to identify a common set of objectives, solutions, drivers, pressures, and trends related to achieving a water-smart society.

KEYWORDS

Water smart solutions, roadmap, circular economy.

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1 Introduction

WP6 aims to develop and implement a roadmap for wider uptake of water-smart solutions that can guide the users to achieve a water-smart society. This document, D6.3, is the first in a series of deliverables to develop the roadmap. The intention of the roadmap and a water-smart is therefore included as an introduction together with a brief description of the outline of this report and the workflow for this objective in WP6.

A roadmap enables decision makers to plan and implement a pathway to achieve desired objectives through a roadmapping process. The objectives in the scope of WIDER UPTAKE are related to fulfilling a water-smart society vision.

According to the definition proposed by Water Europe, a water-smart society is: “a society in which the true value of water is recognized and realized, and all available water sources are managed in such a way that water scarcity and pollution of groundwater and surface water are avoided. Water and resource loops are largely closed to foster a circular economy and optimal resource efficiency, while the water system is resilient against the impact of climate change events” (Water Europe, 2017). WIDER UPTAKE embraces this definition as the vision guiding the creation of roadmaps resulting from the roadmap exercise proposed.

Chapter 2 presents literature findings and describes important general aspects to organise the roadmap exercise for the adaptation in any city or region.

To perform a roadmap exercise, besides dedicated workshops, also data should be available and organized to serve as inputs to the different steps of a roadmap creation or depicting the results of each step. Chapter 3 provides the structure of a roadmap database for the required information to support the exercise. It is expected that the database described in chapter 3 will further inform the functional requirements of the WIDER UPTAKE database (developed in WP2, Task 2.1.2) for supporting roadmapping exercises.

Chapter 4 presents the WIDER UPTAKE demonstration case studies of symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES) from the roadmapping perspective. Some of the cases joined the project with already a clear strategic plan to be implemented during the project duration, while others can benefit from the adoption of the roadmapping exercise to support their further development. To understand the level of maturity of each case, their solutions have been shortly described and discussed in relation to the state of the art for their solutions, what stage of implementation they are at, and what the focus of further development using the roadmap guide could be.

Data for each case study acquired previously and relevant for the scoping step, is presented in chapter 5 following the proposed template described in chapter 2 and discussed to identify a common set of objectives, solutions, drivers, pressures, and trends related to achieving a water-smart society.

WP6 should provide two outcomes for users that wish to apply the knowledge generated in the project as they move along their own path to develop water-smart, and sustainable SCES:

1. A compilation of the results/experiences/insights gained by WIDER UPTAKE and our recommendations for how one should achieve more uptake of water-smart and sustainable SCES and a transition to a water-smart society.
2. A template for creating a roadmap for a specific case aligned with bullet 1 and including the methods and tools developed in WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5.

To achieve the first bullet point, an analysis of results/experiences/insights gained through the activities in WIDER UPTAKE, including the application of the roadmap guide on the selected cases, should be prepared as a report (D6.8, due in month 48) presenting a strategic level discussion and concluding with recommendations for achieving wider uptake of water-smart solutions.

To achieve the second bullet point, WP6 will initially develop a first version of the roadmap guide (D6.6, due in month M36), also termed a roadmap tool, providing the general approach and supporting templates to perform roadmapping exercises. Thereafter, a final version of the roadmap guide will be prepared (D6.7, due in month M48).

D6.7 will take account of lessons learnt after testing the approach for selected cases and be informed by the discussion in section 5 of this document (D6.3), and the outcome of the discussion in the deliverable D6.4 (due in month M42).

The discussion in D6.3 specifies the potential/generalised solutions, drivers, pressures, and trends related to achieving the objectives of a water-smart society by providing a synthesis of the examples collected from the demonstration cases, in addition to specifying the database structure required for the data.

In D6.4 common features in the scenarios used for the testing of the methods and tools developed in WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 will be identified to provide a set of future scenarios that will be included for further use in the roadmap guide, and an analysis of the demonstration cases in view of the developed scenarios.

The description of the general roadmap exercise steps in D6.6 will thus be enriched by further information specific to the context of developing water-smart and sustainable SCES, i.e., potential objectives, solutions, drivers, pressures, trends and future scenarios based on the discussion in D6.3 and D6.4 and be further informed by the input from the final tasks of WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Both versions of the roadmap guide will be uploaded in the Water Europe Market Place, with D6.7 replacing D6.6.

Figure 1: Sequence and timeline of roadmap deliverables

2 The roadmap approach of WIDER UPTAKE

2.1 Literature background

Relevant literature has been considered for setting up the roadmap approach and guidance to run roadmapping exercises. Several definitions of “a roadmap” can be found in literature as it follows:

- A roadmap is one instrument of strategic planning that gives guidance to concrete aspects (actions e.g., legislation) of expected facts (final goals), from TRUST project (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement n° 265122), (Hein et al. 2010).
- Roadmaps conflate and combine three different ways of understanding the future: expectations (what is thought likely to happen), desires (what is hoped will happen) and promises (what will be made to happen), from McDowall et al. (2012).
- A roadmap is a specialised type of strategic plan that outlines activities an organisation can undertake over specified time frames to achieve stated goals and outcomes, from IEA (2014).

The three definitions point at different decision levels’ ambitions with corresponding level of detail for the required input. The one of TRUST is clearly supporting long-term strategic planning at regional or at a vast territory level, while the second one could be related even to individual technological development, but still at a strategic (long-term) level. According to the definition by IEA, a roadmap represents a tool that clearly should outline the links among tasks and priorities for action in the near, medium, and long term. An effective roadmap also includes metrics and milestones to allow regular tracking of progress towards the roadmap’s ultimate goals. What is clear is that whatever the domain of the control actions is (legislation or a single technology), a roadmap is developed to achieve a long-term vision through the identification of precise steps to be performed from today to the long-term time horizon. Within WU, the SCES in the demonstration case studies are assessed according to technical, environmental, social, economic and governance properties to understand how water-smart and sustainable they are. These aspects are needed to allow the transition from a linear to a circular economy model in the water sector (Mannina et al., 2022).

A technology roadmap is intended to support the development of a specific type of technology. The involved stakeholders typically include technical experts, policy makers, sector analysts, researchers, and frontrunners in the relevant sector, who jointly outline performance targets, pathways and priorities and timeframes to accelerate the research, development, and implementation process (Park et al., 2020). Moreover, a technology and strategic roadmapping process mobilizes structured systems thinking, visual methods (e.g., roadmap ‘canvas’) and participative approaches to address organizational challenges and opportunities, supporting communication and alignment for strategic planning and innovation management within and between organizations at firm and sector levels (ibid.).

Beside technology and corporate roadmaps, which tend to focus on the relationship between technology, markets and products, another school within roadmapping focuses on the sectoral and national levels and emphasizes the development of visual narratives describing multi-layered strategy maps of both macro-level trends, micro-level developments, and forward-looking policy design (Ahlqvist et al., 2012). Among these, we see a growing interest in sectoral roadmaps where a wider systems perspective is applied. For example, Haddad and Maldonado (2017) provide an approach where the ‘functions of innovation systems’ are used as drivers/layers in the roadmap, in order to direct decision-making and policy-making efforts towards the functions (e.g., entrepreneurial activities, knowledge development, knowledge diffusion, guidelines and standards, market formation, resource mobilisation, creation of legitimacy/acceptance).

Of course, depending on the control actions in focus, the arena of involved stakeholders and the nature of the alternatives to be compared will differ.

To prepare the WIDER UPTAKE guide for roadmapping, it is required to define:

- the time Horizon for the “long-term” vision
- the domain for control actions (to be taken versus potential scenarios) being for instance in the hands of a board of national decision makers, or a team running a single technological case study.

In WIDER UPTAKE, the time scales to be adopted was discussed in a dedicated session held at the general assembly in 2022 (see MS 8 report for more details). The need to differentiate between short-term, mid-term and long-term was identified. The discussion brought to the analysis of pros and cons of possible selections of long-term, i.e., 2030 and 2050, without conclusion, leaving the option of selection as starting point of the roadmapping exercise. D6.7 will further discuss and advice on the recommended target as long-term time horizon for roadmapping learning from the experience gained along the project.

In relation to the objectives to be prioritized and the potential control actions to be assessed, they result from the negotiation among different decision maker’s objectives and their potential contributions (being the water utility the minimum scale of application). Relevant actors and stakeholders involved in the road mapping process are people and representatives of institutions, who are competent to contribute to the roadmap process and who are crucial for a successful transfer of the roadmap measures and results.

2.2 The WIDER UPTAKE Roadmapping exercise

This chapter describes important general aspects to organise the roadmap exercise proposed in WIDER UPTAKE for the adaptation in any city or region. The approach is grounded in the one proposed by the TRUST project by Hein *et al.* (2010) and adapted to the scope and domain of WIDER UPTAKE. The general aspects here described will be the basis for the creation of the roadmap guide (D6.6) to be tested and revised until its final version (D6.7).

The Roadmapping exercise is the result of the iterative four stages process, consisting of the following: scoping, forecasting, backcasting and transfer (Figure 2). In the following paragraphs details of the roadmap application within WiderUptake are reported.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the roadmap process.

2.2.1 SCOPING: Defining the system and boundaries

Scoping is the first main stage of the roadmapping exercise, which defines the scope of analysis in terms of system descriptions and boundaries. It provides a baseline understanding of today's system and delineates the boundaries. "System" is defined in this deliverable as the SCES and the relevant part of the surrounding environment; further characterization will be possibly adopted in the future D6.6 and D6.7.

This stage identifies relevant actors, asset structures, today's status, and the impact of existing drivers, pressures, and trends on the water management of the city/region as a reference point against which future developments will be addressed.

Scoping focuses on collecting information and gathering knowledge about the objectives of becoming water smarter. This stage must ensure that all relevant parameters and information related to the objectives are available to the core team in order to draw a realistic picture of today's system.

According to scoping, some basic information has to be identified and collected through workshops:

- Determination of the key objectives of the roadmap, its timeframe and perspective.
- Involved actors, stakeholders, institutions, and persons that are important for decision making
- General information about geographical area, spatial boundaries, legal frameworks, and recent developments of the pilot system referring to the demonstration topic
- Information and data about the elements of the system to be analysed in metrics (performance indicators, context information)
- Identification and adjustment of existing pressures and trends on the system

Scoping consists of four working steps:

- S1: Identifying relevant actors
- S2: Objectives of the system
- S3: Elements of the system
- S4: Drivers, pressures, and trends towards a water-smart society

2.2.2 FORECASTING: Envisioning the system in a future world

Forecasting can comprise the following three aspects:

- F1: Projecting possible futures (or scenarios)
- F2: Envisioning the system in the future
- F3: Synthesising

It thus comprises both a projection of the possible future of the external system and a vision of the desired state of the system in the sphere of influence of the user (i.e., the partners of the SCES). A synthesis will test the compatibility of both and identify possible conflicts and needs for remedial adaptive action to be considered in designing the Transfer step.

The rationale of forecasting is to extrapolate current trends into the future, to anticipate new future trends and to obtain a prospective view. The parameters to be forecasted will largely

follow the elements of S3 of the scoping stage but should also anticipate factors which are not considered today.

From a methodological point of view, several methods, both quantitative and qualitative, can be used to perform this task, including (amongst others) time-series methods, interviews with experts, etc. The choice of the optimal method depends on each individual case and the data availability and its degree of detail, but it is common to use a mix of different techniques.

2.2.3 BACKCASTING: Projecting possible visions back into present

In the roadmap, the Backcasting stage builds directly from the Forecasting stage, using the outputs from steps F2 and F3 as a starting point. The overall purpose of this stage is to characterise how a system might shift from its present state to the desired end point. This stage therefore consists of two basic working steps:

- B1: defining intermediate state(s) - The purpose of this working step is to identify and describe at least one intermediate state between the present situation and the (future) vision
- B2: identifying measures to facilitate transitions from state to state - The purpose of this working step is to identify transition measures that will allow the system to shift from its present state towards the intermediate state and the vision.

2.2.4 TRANSFER: Creating the roadmap

The last stage of the roadmapping process is to evaluate the results of analysis and transfer them into a roadmap. This includes providing some chronological information of activities undertaken and results. Creating a roadmap means documenting and transferring identified action fields and measures (defined through workshops) into prioritized recommendations for responsible people and institutions. An adaptive roadmap normally includes listings of relevant action fields and identified measures, indications of prioritisation, time scales and milestones, progress monitoring aspects and an illustration of possible or expected prospects and risks.

In order to organise the transfer of this knowledge into the roadmap effectively, the relevant topics and measures of the system as identified in the preceding step B2 should first be summarised in transfer action fields, and then secondly be evaluated to create the roadmap.

Therefore, Transfer consists of two working steps:

- TR1: Evaluating transfer action fields and their measures: The purpose of this working step is to evaluate the transfer action fields (TA). The measures as defined in Backcasting step B2 should be organized/listed according to this aim (e.g., by a systematic numbering or similar) in a prioritised action plan.

Categories of prioritization are strongly dependent on the action fields and local conditions and should be defined in collaboration with the members of the working group.

- TR2: Creating the roadmap

The achievement of the final roadmap structure will be the result of the interactions with the outcomes derived from WP2-5 and the demonstrations of the water-smart symbiotic solutions in WP1.

The proposed structure, and the way each step is applied may vary due to the local specific conditions of each case study, see chapter 4.

WU provides different instruments to assess transition needs and processes useful at different steps of the roadmap creation. A method for assessing health and quality risks (WP2), methodologies for assessing circularity and resource efficiency (WP3), a governance assessment tool (GOCIWA) and business models (WP4), and a framework for assessing water smartness and sustainability have been developed and tested with the aim of including them in the roadmap guide. As mentioned above, a database for the project with information from the demonstration cases, providing information from the demonstrations and supporting the risk assessment, has been set up in WP2 and it is expected that the database described in chapter 3 will further inform the functional requirements of this database for supporting roadmapping exercises.

3 Database structure

A database with fields for all the required data that should be collected in the roadmapping steps has been developed. The database version included in this deliverable is implemented in MS Excel with a sheet for each case study. Each sheet is organized as reported in Figure 3. More precisely, the database summarizes the metadata related with the demonstration plant position (GPS coordinates), the country and city name. Further, the database is divided into four main fields according to the discussion provided in section 2.2: scoping, forecasting, backcasting and transfer.

In particular, the field “Scoping” is divided into four steps data S1-S4.

Data related with S1 refer to the relevant actors involved in the entire roadmapping process of the case study divided into responsible and others (involved actors, stakeholders, institutions, and persons that are important for decision making).

Data related with S2 refer to the objectives of the system divided into:

- i. type of the objective (e.g., water reuse, sludge reduction, energy production, etc.)
- ii. the motivation to achieve the objective (e.g., cost and energy optimization, regulation etc.)
- iii. Value chain (VC) (e.g., resource recovery, compost production etc.) where “yes” or “no” has to be indicated in the related field. For sake of completeness value chain is here defined as the process or activities by which a company responsible of the demonstration case adds value to a resource including production, marketing, and the provision of after-sales service. Here, the resources involved in the value chain have to be indicated.

Data of step S3 refer to the element of the system. In S3 one has to report: i. if plans exist or not that can favour the achievement of the objectives; ii. the territorial limit (boundary) of the roadmapping process involving the existing plants; iii. the list of the legal framework to refer to; iv. recent development related to the system (e.g., upgrading or new project).

Data of step S4 refer to the drivers, pressures and trends of the process. Drivers are here defined as all social (e.g., social acceptance), regulatory (e.g., foreseen new limitation in existing regulation), environmental, (e.g., existing local standards) and market (e.g., low cost of chemicals to implement the process) conditions that can influence the achievement of the objective. Regarding the pressures the same conditions discussed above (social, regulatory, environmental, and market) considered above have been taken into account considering a negative influence. Finally, in the last part of S4 the database contains information on the observed and future trends that can influence the achievement of the objective. Where the observed trends represent the direction in which the process is developing on the basis of the state of the art conditions (social, regulatory, environmental, and market). While, the future trends represent the direction in which the process is developing on the basis of the

applications of known actions that will favour the achievement of the objective (e.g., future investments).

The field “Forecasting” is divided into three steps data F1-F3.

In F1, future scenarios have to be defined. Scenarios are here defined as “alternative futures” which represent different system states due to the change of facts that cannot be directly controlled (population, climate, economic).

In F2, information about the system in the future has to be inserted (e.g., how do the alternatives future influence the amount of the recovered resources).

Finally, in F3 the conclusions related with F1 and F2 have to be summarized.

In terms of backcasting, database is divided into two main steps: i. the definition of the intermediate states for which at least three states are suggested (within the project duration, mid-term state - 2026 and long-term state - 2030); ii. list of the measure to facilitate transition from state to state (e.g., upgrading the design existing plants etc.).

Regarding the “transfer” field data of the two main steps (TR1 and TR2) have to be summarized. In particular, the list of the actions to achieve the objectives and the key information about the roadmap have to be inserted.

Annex 1 contains the Excel sheet database structure. Data for each case study acquired previously and relevant for the scoping step have been added and provide the basis for the discussion in Chapter 5 to identify a common set of objectives, solutions, drivers, pressures, and trends related to achieving a water-smart society.

METADATA										
Position (GPS coordinates)	Country	City								
(insert here GPS Coordinates)	(insert here the country name)	(insert here the city name)								
SCOPING										
S1				S2						
Relevant actors			Objectives of the system							
Responsible	Others: involved actors, stakeholders, institutions, and persons that are	Type	Motivation	VC: Water reuse	VC: Nutrient recovery	VC: Compost production	VC: Manufacturing of products	VC: Energy recovery	Due	
E.g. plants operators, utility, government...	List all the relevant actors involved	Insert type of objective e.g. water reuse, energy production...	Insert here the motivation to achieve the objective e.g., cost and energy optimization, regulation, ...	Insert yes or no	Insert yes or no	Insert yes or no	Insert yes or no	Insert yes or no	Insert data	
S3										
Element of the system										
Existing plans	Boundary	framework	Recent development							
Insert yes or no	Insert here the limit of the boundary and areas	List the legal framework to refer to	Insert here if the plants have been subjected to upgrading or other							
S4										
Drivers				Pressures				Trends		
Social	Regulatory	Enviroment	Market	Social	Regulatory	Enviroment	Market	Observed trends	Future trends or development	
Explain	Explain	Explain	Explain	Explain	Explain	Explain	Explain	E.g. increasing energy consumption, increasing level of water smart...	E.g. the current level will increase thank to investments...or viceversa	
FORECASTING			BACKCASTING						TRANSFER	
F1	F2	F3	B1			B2			TR1	TR2
Projecting possible futures (or scenarios)	Visioning the system in the future	Synthesis	Intermediate states			Measure to facilitate transition from state to state			Transfer action fields and their measures	Creating the roadmap
			Within project duration	Insert a short term state data	Insert a long term state data	Within project duration	Insert short term state	Insert long term state		
Define here scenarios (lists of altenative future)	How does the system will be for each alternative future?	Summarize here the relevant element that merit to be emphasized		Suggested: 2026.	Suggested: 2030.	Insert here the measures that have to be implemented within the project duration for the ojctives achievement	Insert here the measures that have to be implemented within 2026 for the ojctives achievement	Insert here the measures that have to be implemented within 2030 for the ojctives achievement	List the measures and action fields	Summarize here the relevant element of the roadmap that merit to be emphasized
VC = Value Chain										

Figure 3: Database structure

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4 Case study description from a Roadmap perspective

4.1 The Italian case study in Corleone

Objective

The main objectives of this case study are the recovery of several materials to be used as circular economy value chains such as water from treated wastewater, production of compost from sewage sludge to be used as fertilizer and reduction of waste sludge production.

Expected impacts

The recovered materials can have a market, thus providing a profit to the water utility and industrial synergy. The waste sludge reduction might contribute to reduce the wastewater treatment plant operational costs and environmental impacts such as GHG emissions.

Ambition

Within Wider – Uptake AMAP Spa has the aim to break the barriers that hamper the water reuse and resource recovery from wastewater treatment by means of a synergic support from the University of Palermo activities, in particular in the following key activities:

- Re-start of the ultrafiltration plant at Corleone WWTP for agricultural and civil water reuse;
- Assembly of equipment (e.g., flow meters, air diffuser system, etc.) to Corleone WWTP with the aim to improve monitoring and plant operation;
- Meeting with local stakeholders and policy makers.

Description of the SCES(s) – including if appropriate, challenges and development needs

Water reuse is expected to be applied to Corleone WWTP since large previous investments have been done to realize a water reuse system made-up of: an ultrafiltration plant for producing water to be reused; a pipe-line system for transferring treated water to three storing lakes and three storing lakes. However, due to administrative/organizational/technical challenges/barriers the water reuse in Corleone is currently not in operation. Therefore, Corleone Municipality has an urgent need to restart the water reuse system to justify previous investments and, more importantly, to apply a real transition to a circular economy. With this regard, within Wider-Uptake activities aimed at boosting water reuse in Corleone, Unipa promoted and signed in 2020 a Memorandum of Understanding between the Special Unique Commissioner for Wastewater Treatment Facilities (from the Environmental Italian Ministry) and the national association of Italian municipalities, to enhance wastewater treatment in the region. Furthermore, Unipa prepared jointly with main stakeholders involved in water reuse in Corleone, two new projects titled "REcupero di Materie ed energia dalle Acque Reflue per la creazione di un ecosistema sostenibile nella città di Corleone – REMARC" and "IL Riuso delle acque reflue depurate secondo un approccio di economia circolare a Corleone e Marineo –

RICOM" have been recently proposed. REMARC and RICOM projects have been conceived with the aim to overcome some barriers identified within the Wider-Uptake H2020 Project with the final aim to implement water reuse in Corleone case study. Further, application of new calls for fund raising have been prepared with the idea to find the economic funds for restoring the hydraulic infrastructures in Corleone which are not in operation and are damaged because of aging (i.e., pipe line from Corleone's WWTP, storing lakes nearby Corleone's WWTP and irrigation network for farmers).

4.2 The Ghanaian case study in Accra

Objective

The main aims of this case study are represented by the reuse of wastewater, conversion of sludge into biochar to replace wood-based charcoal and reduction of waste sludge production.

Expected impacts

The expected impacts will include the reduction in reliance of wood-based charcoal, thus helping reduce deforestation, the reduction in use of untreated wastewater for urban farming and the production of healthy and safe vegetables for the city population. The recovery and use of both treated wastewater and biochar would also provide economic, environmental (e.g., reduction of GHG emissions) and social benefits.

Ambition

Regarding the ambition of the project, WIDER UPTAKE will go beyond state of the art in sludge management, in wastewater treatment for resource recovery as well as in the use of wastewater for urban agriculture.

Description of the SCES(s) – including if appropriate, challenges and development needs

The Sewerage Systems Ghana Limited (SSGL) signed a public-private partnership management contract with the Ministry of Local Government to operate the Mudor Treatment Plant. The plant treats wastewater from Accra, the capital of Ghana, and has a capacity of 18 000 m³/day. According to Environmental Sanitation Policy (ESP), a response to the increasing waste volumes and changing waste in Ghana calls for activities that “ensure adequate systems for managing wastewater treatment, re-use, and disposal.” Thus, this demonstration seeks to show the way in terms of resource recovery from wastewater and water re-use in Ghana. It is important to note that the ESP is long due for a review and update. Hence, lessons being learned from this demonstration can go to feed into the policy revision process.

Notwithstanding the above, the ESP does not provide a clear roadmap towards the realisation of the measures. In addition, there are no locally developed standards for resources recovered from wastewater treatment although there are standards for effluent discharge. Hence, lessons from this demonstration will be important for consideration into developing standards for treated wastewater re-use for various needs.

4.3 The Dutch case study in Amsterdam

Objective

The key objectives of the case study are represented by developing, optimizing, demonstrating and preparing for market uptake new bio composite materials from water embedded resources; this also involves manufacturability of the materials and the development of prototype products for demonstration.

Expected impact

The expected impacts are represented by the following:

- accelerated availability and adoption of new and optimized biocomposites on the basis of recovered raw materials and residuals from the water cycle;
- identification of (remaining) barriers for a wider availability and upscaling of those bio composites and their ingredients;
- demonstrating circular use of water-embedded resources, and its potential thereof, in support of sustainability goals of the Water Boards;
- increased awareness for and confidence in utilising bio- and waste streams from the water cycle and in the applicability of bio composite materials developed thereof resulting in an improved market potential for these.

Ambition

The ambition is to lower the application gaps and barriers for adoption that exist for bio-composites in comparison with conventional materials. Make bio composites with bio- and waste streams from the water cycle a viable alternative to less sustainable materials such as glass composites, aluminium and tropical hard wood.

Description of the SCES(s) – including if appropriate, challenges and development needs

Recycled calcite from the softening of drinking water has received the status of by-product. The application for cellulose recovered from wastewater (Recell[®]) is still under review. If resource recovered from wastewater, such as cellulose fibres, would not receive an end of waste status, this would leave an unequal level playing field with virgin materials and provide a threshold/standard for adoption for a bio composite material containing such ‘waste’ stream.

With regard to the waste status of biomass, a legal judgment on the use of grass clippings from ecological management for cardboard production is current case law. After a judicial review, it has been determined that – subject to conditions – the described use of clippings in this case concerns ‘continued use’ and not a ‘removal’ (i.e., waste). Users of grass or reed from ecological nature management remain responsible at all times for verifying whether the set criteria are met in their specific use case, which includes a traceable origin and a supply chain dedicated for the intended use (separate from waste treatment) in an application with sufficiently high

resource efficiency (higher than waste). This case law is not valid for export, which restricts cross-border activity.

Waternet's main activities in WIDER UPTAKE are to supply raw materials from the water cycle for production of biocomposites, and in turn demonstrate the use of biocomposite products in a demo site. The price for the biocomposites will be higher than for conventional materials (for example when considering replacing tropical hardwood used for piers along canals), therefore marketing is crucial.

NPSP's goals in WIDER UPTAKE are to develop improved biocomposite materials and adapted production processes, systematically test and assess the new material, and optimize and (preferably) automate production. TU Delft is helping to develop methods and conduct some of these assessments (wide range of risk, circularity, efficiency, etc.).

The existing infrastructure promotes the transition to a circular economy as resource recovery is already being done. However, there is a lack of cellulose seething stations that would contribute to more resource recovery from wastewater.

The main barriers for adoption of alternative materials lies in a combination between technical, economic and governance issues related to the use of biocomposites in riverbank protection. The technical side concerns, for the moment lack of proof of concept and documentation on the qualities of biocomposites in riverbank protections. The economic and governance aspects connect in the process of public procurement, where these processes at present do not emphasise sustainability aspects of public procurement thoroughly, thus more sustainable options are not competitive when purchasers conduct cost-benefit analyses of different options.

This unique case study will explore the production and applications e.g., construction materials in river/canal bank protection elements, modular facade panels, and circular one lamp, of a new biocomposite material made by recovering resources from drinking water treatment (calcite), wastewater treatment (cellulose fibres) and surface water management (water plants), all glued together using a bio-based resin.

4.4 The Norwegian case study in Hamar and Stavanger

Objective

The main objectives of the case study are represented by:

- Wider introduction of an innovative continuous biofilm process enabling 50% P-recovery from wastewater in a process with high energy efficiency and self-supplied or net producer of energy.
- Production of organic fertilizers and struvite or balanced fertilizer products that are tailored to circular economy value chains.

- Production of a commercial organic fertilizer based on biosolids/waste water sludge with NPK-content equivalent to industrially produced mineral fertilizers.

Expected impacts

The impacts expected by the project will ensure:

- the P-recovery (> 50%) contributes to improved recovery and use of resources.
- increased potential for market uptake for the existing production of organic fertilizers and inorganic fertilizers in the Minorga process by use of P from the treatment plants.

Ambition

The ambition of the demonstration is represented by the following: going beyond state of the art in nutrient recovery; going beyond state of the art in wastewater treatment for resource recovery and going beyond the state of the art by utilizing biogas from sludge digestion in a natural gas energy grid.

Description of the SCES(s) – including if appropriate, challenges and development needs

The demonstration in Norway includes activity at HIAS, in the eastern, inland part of Norway, and IVAR, in the south-western county called Rogaland. Together, the two inter-municipal companies treat a total load of 570 000 pe municipal and industrial wastewater. The wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are in the process of converting from chemical phosphorus removal to enhanced biological phosphorus removal (EBPR). HIAS is implementing an innovative continuous moving bed biofilm reactor (MBBR) process in collaboration with HIAS How2O. Biogas is produced by digestion of the sludge. Struvite precipitation for P-recovery will be implemented in full scale to recover 18-30 tons P/year. The third partner, Sirkula, is producing biosolids from various organic waste including wastewater sludge and aims to develop new soil products as part of the activity in WIDER UPTAKE. At IVAR there is co-digestion of food waste and sludge, and the biogas is adjusted and injected into the natural gas grid for the region. Grønn Vekst produces pelletized organic fertilizer from the residual sludge.

4.5 The Czech case study in Prague

Objective

The main objectives of the case study are represented by the reuse of wastewater and the consequent reduction of drinking water use for urban irrigation and cleaning the city streets.

Expected impacts

The expected impacts are represented by the reduction in use of clean drinking water from the city networks for urban irrigation as well as changing of microclimate of the city using treated water for more frequent irrigation and cleaning of the streets.

Ambition

The ambition of demonstration is to go beyond state of the art in using treated water for urban irrigation and go beyond state of treated water disinfection for irrigation and public city use.

Description of the SCES(s) – including if appropriate, challenges and development needs

In Prague, severe flood damage led the city to build a new state-of-the-art water line on Císarský Island (2015-2019). This is an area with extensive vegetation to be irrigated with drinking water. The potential to reduce the current overuse of groundwater, as well as transport costs, is a push towards water reuse. There is also potential for new blue-green infrastructure for surface water management. From 2022-2023, the reconstruction of the existing water line may provide an opportunity to implement EC innovations. In addition, the city of Prague has declared EC ambitions, including better use of organic waste and urban organic farming to reduce municipal waste by 50% by 2030. It has bought back and transferred 49% of the Veolia-owned water company PVK to PVS, owned by the city, for better control of plans and prices. However, the systems are bureaucratic, and the distribution of responsibilities is unclear, for example, water reuse units and irrigation networks exist but lack maintenance. One of the specific factors that could support and accelerate the introduction of water reuse in the Czech Republic is the drought that the country experienced in the period 2014 - 2019. According to the Climatechange.com server(<https://www.climatechange.com/czech-republic/droughts/>) the period 2014 - 2019 was a dry period in most of Europe, the worst multi-year soil moisture drought in 253 years (1766 - 2018), especially in Central Europe. Ecosystems such as forests can sustain droughts of only one year. Repeated exposure to the stress of multi-year droughts, however, can lead to serious damage. The multi-year drought of 2014 - 2019 was primarily a soil drought. It was not due to significant rainfall deficits, but to high temperatures that increased the evaporation of soil moisture. The severity of the soil moisture drought followed the same spatial pattern as the temperature anomalies. The multi-year drought particularly affected Germany, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, the Baltic States and Sweden.

The multi-year drought of 2014 - 2019 increased the acceptance of the use of treated wastewater as a new water resource in many Czech municipalities when people could see that effluents from municipal wastewater treatment plants were discharged into receiving bodies with a much more stable flow than the flow of the rivers or streams themselves. This period was also coincidentally the time when the new water line of the Prague Central WWTP was built and completed (2015 - 2019). The Prague Central WWTP occupies most of Císarský (Emperor's Island) on the Vltava River. Of course, this island, which is the last one downstream of the Vltava River in the city, is also a place with the lowest altitude.

The demonstration irrigation units built as part of the Wider Uptake project on Císarský Island in Prague consist of four separate boxes, each divided into three fields for the cultivation of typical urban park greenery, i.e., grass, various flowers, and bushes. The boxes are irrigated by four different water sources:

1. Water from the Vltava River,
2. Final effluent from the new water line of the central sewage treatment plant in Prague,
3. Final effluent disinfected with a UV lamp,
4. Final effluent treated with membrane ultrafiltration and UV lamp.

4.6 Characteristics of the demonstration case studies

This section provides a discussion of the demonstration case studies with relation to state of the art for their solutions, what stage of implementation they are at, and what the focus of further development using the roadmap guide could be.

Table 1: Characteristics of the demonstration case studies.

Demonstration case and solution(s)	Relation to state of the art	Current stage of implementation	Potential focus of further development using the roadmap guide
Corleone – reuse of polished WWTP effluent for agricultural irrigation and compost from WWTP sludge	<p>Reuse of polished WWTP effluent after UF is state of the art and used by several.</p> <p>Production of compost from sewage sludge to be used as fertilizer is state of the art and used by several.</p> <p>Reduction of waste sludge production by optimised WWTP configuration is state of the art.</p>	<p>Technical solutions are investigated in pilot scale at UNIPA.</p> <p>Full scale implementation of technical solutions is being prepared and in progress at the WWTP in Corleone, but not in operation for demonstration of the solution.</p> <p>In view of roadmapping, some steps have already been taken; indeed, referring to the Scoping step, a CoP was created, and in the frame of forecasting, future scenarios have been imagined. Based on the inputs received from the CoP, which have been extended with additional stakeholders, new projects have been proposed, in order to overcome the existing barriers.</p>	<p>The technical solutions have been selected previously. Further development and implementation have been proposed for national funding.</p> <p>Further development related to policy/governance aspects and development of value chains with business models for the partners of the SCESs may benefit from use of a roadmap process.</p>
Accra – reuse of polished WWTP effluent for irrigation in urban agriculture and production of biochar from WWTP	<p>Reuse of polished WWTP effluent for irrigation in urban agriculture with a polishing step consisting of filtration and activated carbon, supplemented by</p>	<p>Polishing of treated wastewater and biochar production has been implemented in large pilot scale.</p>	<p>Further development of the SCESs with respect to alternative technical solutions for the logistics and disinfection of the polished wastewater, alternative uses of biochar from WWTP sludge, and alternatives to</p>

<p>sludge as substitute for wood-based charcoal</p>	<p>disinfection is not as advanced as similar solutions with membrane filtration.</p> <p>The integrated disinfection effect due to sunlight in the shallow water storage reservoir at the farming site is an innovative solution. However, the effect, needs to be assessed compared to disinfection by chemicals at the WWTP before transport.</p> <p>Considering the current practise of using untreated wastewater the solution progresses beyond state of the art in the local context.</p> <p>Biochar as a substitute for wood-based charcoal is an innovative solution with potential advantages with respect to reduced deforestation provided the solution can be upscaled.</p>	<p>Use of the polished wastewater for irrigation and use of biochar in SMEs has been implemented in full scale at selected test sites.</p> <p>Stakeholder interaction and policy dialogue are part of the activity that has been done and recognised as a requirement for further development of the solutions.</p>	<p>biochar for sludge management that may benefit from a roadmapping process.</p> <p>Further development related to policy/governance aspects should be included, as should development of value chains with business models for the partners of the SCEs.</p> <p>The required roadmapping process would therefore need to include both technical development and policy/governance and market-related aspect.</p>
<p>Amsterdam – biocomposite material from recovered resources from the water sector and products made from the biocomposite material</p>	<p>The development, optimization, demonstration, and preparation for market uptake of state-of-the-art bio-composite materials made from water-embedded resources.</p>	<p>Applications:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Solar panel framing, – Not pursued (cost economics, WATNL disinterest); 2) Building facade elements – N8012/N8020 tiles; exhibited at DDW 2021, Floriade 2022; to be deployed at WANT in Q3 2023; 3) Household furniture (tabletop and chair shells) – Not pursued within project (cost economics, lack of opportunity); 4) Riverbank stabilization elements – N8010 reference application trial site WATNL; pilot extension trial site at 	<p>Objectives for further development that would benefit from roadmapping :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of market and value chains (mainly facades and bank protection); <p>Further production and testing of different recipes;</p> <p>Development of business model along with commercial business development and exploration of partnering options;</p> <p>Continued positioning of NPSP on the market;</p> <p>Strategic re-orientation and financing, required for scaling up.</p>

		<p>WATNL with N8012, N8020 and N8040 corrugated panels in Q3 2023;</p> <p>5) Public space furniture like traffic signs and street benches – N8010 benches and traffic sign showcases, water level scales trial at WATNL;</p> <p>6) Weirs and baffles – N8010 weir trial project at WATNL; N8010 baffle trial project in Q2 2023 (May);</p> <p>7) Circular One spherical lamp – Selection of N8012/N8020/ N8040 lamps at WATNL; manufacturing in Q2 2023 (Apr-May);</p> <p>8) Restaurant trays (optional) – Interest confirmed at WATNL.</p>	
<p>Hamar – struvite and peat free soil products from WWTP sludge</p>	<p>Enhanced biological Phosphorus removal (EBPR) from wastewater in a full-scale continuous biofilm process is innovative and beyond state of the art represented by various activated sludge process configurations for EBPR.</p> <p>Recovering phosphorus from EBPR sludge by struvite is state of the art and has been implemented previously.</p> <p>Production of soil products from WWTP sludge and other organic waste fractions is state of the art. Using WWTP sludge with reduced phosphorus content as a substitute for peat-based ingredients is innovative and give a product with reduced phosphorus leaching.</p>	<p>The solutions at the WWTP, i.e., the continuous EBPR biofilm process and phosphorus recovery as struvite is implemented in full scale.</p> <p>The soil production process from composted organic fractions has been implemented in full scale previously and will include the sludge after P-recovery when this becomes available.</p>	<p>The technical solutions for phosphorus recovery have been selected and are in place.</p> <p>Further developments of the solution implemented at Hias are related to market uptake of the continuous MBBR process for EBPR and the value chain and market for struvite.</p> <p>For the soil products testing of different recipes is foreseen, but the technical aspects of soil production from compost are to a large extent known.</p> <p>Further developments may be influenced by the outcome of the ongoing revision of the Norwegian regulation for sludge and organic fertiliser products and may benefit from analysing several potential future scenarios.</p>

			Such aspects may benefit from a roadmapping process and use of the roadmapping guide.
Stavanger – upgraded biogas and organic fertiliser from WWTP sludge	<p>Enhanced biological Phosphorus removal (EBPR) from wastewater in a full-scale activated sludge is state of the art, although it is applied to diluted and cold wastewater which may be challenging.</p> <p>Biogas production is enhanced by improving the primary treatment by applying polymer to increase the primary sludge production. The biogas production is further enhanced by co-digestion of sewage sludge, private and industrial food waste, and fish farming sludge. This has been done before, but is considered to be beyond state of the art.</p> <p>Upgrading the biogas to natural gas specifications and distributing to existing natural gas grid is innovative but state of the art technology.</p> <p>Production of dried pelletized organic fertilizer and struvite fertilizer are both state of the art technologies.</p>	<p>The full scale EBPR has been implemented, but the process solution needs to be optimized.</p> <p>Test trials with polymers in the primary treatment has been conducted. Tests with co-digestion for biogas production has also been conducted.</p> <p>Upgrading of the biogas and distribution to the existing natural gas grid has been implemented.</p> <p>Full scale production of pelletized organic fertilizer has been implemented. Pilot tests with struvite precipitation is being prepared.</p>	<p>Further technical fine tuning/modification followed by optimization is needed for the EBPR WWTP and the biogas production facilities.</p> <p>Further implementation of solutions for organic fertilizer and struvite will depend on the development of the value chain and market for pelletized organic fertilizer and struvite.</p> <p>Further developments may be influenced by the outcome of the ongoing revision of the Norwegian regulation for sludge and organic fertiliser products and may benefit from analysing several potential future scenarios.</p> <p>These aspects may benefit from a roadmapping process and use of the roadmapping guide.</p>
Prague – recovered wastewater for irrigation of urban green areas	Treating the effluent from the city WWTP with UV lamps, which is the most probable option to be implemented during the project, is the state-of-the-art if we rule	Currently, most of the chemical analyses are finished and inserted into the database.	The goal of the current stage is to build on our experiments with water-irrigation boxes, finish the chemical analyses and

	<p>out the experimental methods of treatment applied to reclaimed rainwater or seawater. For municipal wastewater both UV-disinfection and UF can be considered state-of-the-art technologies.</p>	<p>Simultaneously, a data analysis system using AI is being implemented in our database web-app to allow users to come to preliminary conclusions regarding recycled water with the provided parameters. Both accumulation and analysis of the data at the tip of users' fingers will serve as a foundation for a data-driven framework that facilitates water reclamation and reuse.</p> <p>A progress is being made in terms of communication with stakeholders and various plans for the future of reusing wastewater are discussed.</p>	<p>catalogue all the experimental data acquired during the project.</p> <p>It is important to settle for a manner of supervision in pilot projects with the recycled water. What chemical tests to run and how often.</p> <p>It is imperative that we solve the logistic problems of transportation of the recycled water in case of someone's interested from the other part of the city.</p> <p>AI data analysis is to be thoroughly tested.</p>
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5 Main outcome/insights of the filled database

In this chapter, the results related with each case study will be presented (Table 2 - Table 5) and discussed in relation to the scoping step. The information is provided in the form of discussion across the different cases as a synopsis to inform the roadmap guide that will be developed as D6.7. D6.7 will make use of the information here provided to customize the roadmapping exercise to the scope of WIDER UPTAKE by learning from the experience and work performed by the case studies in relation to common objectives, solutions, drivers, pressures and trends.

Table 2: Overview of data provided for step S1

Demonstration case and solution(s)	S1: Relevant actors
Corleone – reuse of polished WWTP effluent for agricultural irrigation and compost from WWTP sludge	Responsible: AMAP Spa Others involved in the symbiotic solution: UNIPA CoP: established
Accra – reuse of polished WWTP effluent for irrigation in urban agriculture and production of biochar from WWTP sludge as substitute for wood-based charcoal	Responsible: CSIR Others involved in the symbiotic solution: SSGL, SINTEF CoP: established
Amsterdam – biocomposite material from recovered resources from the water sector and products made from the biocomposite material	Responsible: NPSP and Waternet Others involved in the symbiotic solution: TU Delft CoP: established
Hamar – struvite and peat free soil products from WWTP sludge	Responsible: Utility (Hias IKS) and Utility (Sirkula IKS) Others involved in the symbiotic solution: NTNU, IVAR, HØST, Hias H2O, SINTEF CoP: established
Stavanger – upgraded biogas and organic fertiliser from WWTP sludge	Responsible: IVAR, HØST Others involved in the symbiotic solution: NTNU, HIAS, HØST, SINTEF CoP: established
Prague – recovered wastewater for irrigation of urban green areas	Responsible: CVUT Others involved in the symbiotic solution: VSCHT, Storm Aqua, PVS CoP: established

Table 3: Overview of data provided for step S2

Demonstration case and solution(s)	S2: Objectives of the system
Corleone – reuse of polished WWTP effluent for agricultural irrigation and compost from WWTP sludge	Type: Water reuse, sewage sludge reduction, WWTP optimization and reduction of GHG emissions. Motivation: Reduction operating costs, resource (water) recovery. Selected VC: water reuse. Due: 2026.
Accra – reuse of polished WWTP effluent for irrigation in urban agriculture and production of	Type: Water reuse, sewage sludge reuse, reduction in sludge production Motivation: Reducing operational cost of WWTP, resource recovery, reduction in deforestation

biochar from WWTP sludge as substitute for wood-based charcoal	Selected VC: water reuse and reduction in sludge production Due: 2023
Amsterdam – biocomposite material from recovered resources from the water sector and products made from the biocomposite material	Type: Development, optimization, demonstration and preparation for market uptake of new bio composite materials based on resources recovered from the watercycle. Motivation: Make bio composites with bio- and waste streams Selected VC: Resource recovery. Due: 2024.
Hamar – struvite and peat free soil products from WWTP sludge	Type: Phosphorus recovery, Peat free soil products Motivation: WWTP retrofitting, P-recovery, cost reduction, environmental impact reduction, new revenue creation, utilisation of treated sewage sludge, protection of peat areas. Selected VC: Nutrient recovery, compost production. Due: 2024.
Stavanger – upgraded biogas and organic fertiliser from WWTP sludge	Type: Biogas to local gas grid, organic fertiliser from sewage sludge. Motivation: Replacement of gas for fossil sources, increase circularity, revenue creation, Produce organic fertiliser from dried sewage sludge with eventual addition of additives as required. Selected VC: Resource recovery (as organic fertiliser) and energy recovery. Due: 2024
Prague – recovered wastewater for irrigation of urban green areas	Type: Water reuse Motivation: Conserve water resources, reduce demand on other water sources, improve park health and appearance, and reduce need for chemical fertilizers and pesticides, social and economic benefits. Selected VC: water reuse Due: 2028

Table 4: Overview of data provided for step S3

Demonstration case and solution(s)	S3: Element of the system
Corleone – reuse of polished WWTP effluent for agricultural irrigation and compost from WWTP sludge	Existing plan: yes Boundary: The boundary depends on the future alternative Legal framework: Decreto del Ministero dell'Ambiente 185/2003 (current national), Legge Regionale Sicilia n. 4 del 22 marzo 2022 (local), EU Regulation 741/2020 (future) Recent development: “equipment maintenance, installation of flow rate measurement devices, water line will be operated as aerated activated sludge tank + anaerobic side-stream reactor (ASSR) to implement the oxic-settling-anaerobic (OSA) process”.
Accra – reuse of polished WWTP effluent for irrigation in urban agriculture and production of biochar from WWTP sludge as substitute for wood-based charcoal	Existing plan: Yes Boundary: Regional (sub-national) and national in nature. However, these levels depend on future national policies and/or city byelaws Legal framework: None yet Recent development: National awakening and pursuit of circular economy is preparing the grounds to allow for policymaking to proceed and which will enhance the wider uptake of the solutions.

Amsterdam – biocomposite material from recovered resources from the water sector and products made from the biocomposite material	<p>Existing plan: yes</p> <p>Boundary: The boundary depends on the composition and properties of the material. Business wise, the current focus is on The Netherlands, however opportunities arise EU-wide. There are no geo-restrictions (within EU).</p> <p>Legal framework: Waste Directive (e.g., w.r.t. biomass and resources recovered from wastewater).</p> <p>Recent development: Awareness that a small flexible production capacity at NPSP is inevitable for (early) business development (being setup 1H2023) and that production partners willing and capable to produce (dough) and manufacture (press) with natural fibres and waste streams are inevitable for scale up (potentials identified and being visited, but countable EU wide). Cost efficient production requires investments for scale.</p>
Hamar – struvite and peat free soil products from WWTP sludge	<p>Existing plan: yes</p> <p>Boundary: ""</p> <p>Legal framework: ""</p> <p>Recent development: Chemical P-removal to EBPR in continuous MBBR process, Plant for recovery of phosphorus as struvite, Soil products from compost and sewage sludge with reduced P-content after P-recovery</p>
Stavanger – upgraded biogas and organic fertiliser from WWTP sludge	<p>Existing plan: yes</p> <p>Boundary: ""</p> <p>Legal framework: ""</p> <p>Recent development: Demonstrate use of upgraded biogas as replacement of natural gas in local gas grid to reduce CO₂ footprint, Organic fertiliser products.</p>
Prague – recovered wastewater for irrigation of urban green areas	<p>Existing plan: yes</p> <p>Boundary: ""</p> <p>Legal framework: ""</p> <p>Recent development: ""</p>

Table 5: Overview of data provided for step S4

Demonstration case and solution(s)	S4: Drivers, pressures, and trends towards a water smart society
Corleone – reuse of polished WWTP effluent for agricultural irrigation and compost from WWTP sludge	<p>Drivers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social: favourable conditions towards the water-smart transition - Regulatory: The guidelines of the new law 741/2020 have still to be established (national and local) - Environment: Reduction of industrial mineral fertilizers; reduction of natural water use for agricultural purpose - Market: - <p>Pressure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social: Farmers acceptance strongly depends on the water quality - Regulatory: existing regulations do not facilitate the resource reuse process; Absence or weak interaction with policy makers and decision makers - Environment: Reduction of pollutants load in the RWB - Market: - <p>Trends:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Observed trends: AMAP Spa and Municipalities have economic interest in implementing water-smart solutions in view of reducing the plants operating costs.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Future trends or developments: 1) Corleone Municipality strongly interested in using the water reuse system and spread the water reuse; 2) two new projects (REMARC and RICOM) have been submitted in view of finding the funding for the missing infrastructure building.
<p>Accra – reuse of polished WWTP effluent for irrigation in urban agriculture and production of biochar from WWTP sludge as substitute for wood-based charcoal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drivers: - Social: Work needs to be done for nationwide acceptance of crops grown with treated wastewater - Regulatory: At the moment, there is no regulation for resources recovered from wastewater treatment - Environment: There is an increasing interest, at the government level, on issues of circular economy in Ghana - Market: Already, there is reliance on vegetables produced from wastewater in Accra as well as reliance on charcoal for heating - Pressure: - Social: Need to address perceptions of people regarding use of 'waste-products' - Regulatory: At the moment, no regulations exist for resources recovery from wastewater. Hence there is need for such a legislation - Environment: Increasing drought and erratic rainfall - Market: Ensuring confidence that crops grown with treated wastewater are safe for consumption and penetration into the supermarkets with such crops - Trends: - Observed trends: SSGL has great interest in recovering resources from wastewater treatment; there is demand of charcoal as well as increasing patronage of vegetables in the urban centres - Future trends or developments: SSGL is expanding nationwide in construction of wastewater treatment plant; there is increasing demand for charcoal. Furthermore, increasing urbanisation in the future makes the solutions very important - -
<p>Amsterdam – biocomposite material from recovered resources from the water sector and products made from the biocomposite material</p>	<p>Drivers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social: Moving towards more sustainable materials and solutions. - Regulatory: National and International agreements and obligations w.r.t. Climate change (sustainability, energy transition), and Circular Economy. Public sector commitment to have reduced 50% of primary resources in 2030. - Environment: Biodiversity objectives and policies - Market: Companies guided by and judged on sustainability <p>Pressure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social: Resistance to change (e.g., in living standard) - Regulatory: Obtaining end of waste status for resources like cellulose from sewage (Recell®) - Environment: - - Market: Moving towards more sustainable materials and circular economy solutions. <p>Trends:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Observed trends: The market focus is with recycled materials and products for now. - Future trends or developments: Broad willingness to pay for materials and products from renewable resources.
Hamar – struvite and peat free soil products from WWTP sludge	<p>Drivers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social: High public awareness to wastewater release to local waterbodies due to pollution in the neighbouring lake in the past; Public awareness of importance of peat in relation to climate change, and as element in conservation nature - Regulatory: Foreseen P-limitation in revised sludge regulation. - Environment: - - Market: Reduced cost for chemicals, potential market demand <p>Pressure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social: - - Regulatory: Tightened control and stronger enforcement of regulations from national authorities. - Environment: - - Market: - <p>Trends:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Observed trends: increasing energy consumption, increasing awareness to sustainability and circularity - Future trends or developments: Some population growth, increased rainfall
Stavanger – upgraded biogas and organic fertiliser from WWTP sludge	<p>Drivers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social: Climate and circularity goals. - Regulatory: Increasing carbon fee increases the attractiveness of biogas; Regulation change to incentivize fertilizer production from sludge. - Environment: - - Market: Local Energy Company wants to buy biogas. Existing gas grid in the region where biogas can be pumped into. General interest from potential customers towards more sustainable products. <p>Pressure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social: Too much biowaste (manure) in Stavanger area, need to get rid of it somehow. - Regulatory: - - Environment: - - Market: - <p>Trends:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Observed trends: Increasing awareness to sustainability and circularity - Future trends or developments: Some population growth, increased rainfall
Prague – recovered wastewater for irrigation of urban green areas	<p>Drivers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social: It is important to find ways to reuse and recycle water whenever possible. - Regulatory: Discharge regulations, drought management policies in the future, environmental protection laws - Environment:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market: The cost of water, availability of financial incentives and the public perception of water reuse, cut costs of treatment and infrastructure <p>Pressure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social: Low acceptance by the population - Regulatory: - - Environment: - - Market: - <p>Trends:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Observed trends: Consumption of water continues to fall since the 90s. People are conscious about the environment. - Future trends or developments: The geopolitical situation and its economic consequences will probably lead to a more resource-conscious population (that includes water). Higher investments are probable.
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5.1 Discussion

Three of the six demonstration case studies within Wider-Uptake have as the main objective the water reuse (Corleone –IT, Prague and Accra). For the Italian case study (Corleone), the pilot scale experimentation has been completed in view of defining indicators for quantifying quality of reclaimed water in a circular economy and sustainable perspective. The full-scale plant has been subjected to equipment maintenance and installation of new devices before starting with the ultrafiltration system operation for water reuse that is still not in operation. Activities related to water reuse boosting have been carried out to foster the distribution of reused water once the ultrafiltration systems will be in operation (within 2023). While, in Prague extensive pilot scale activities have been performed focused on monitoring the effect on plant growth of different water origin (river or treated wastewater) and treatment (membrane, UV). In Accra sampling and monitoring activities of the soil, wastewater, and vegetables at the CSIR-Water Research Institute (WRI) and CSIR Animal Research Institute (ARI) project site have been performed to establish how to improve water reuse process and products (vegetables) quality. Since the local and infrastructure conditions of these case studies are quite different each other the final objective will be achieved at different times (2026 - Corleone; 2028 – Prague; ‘Not defined’ – Accra). In Accra there is also the aim to reuse sewage sludge. The other three case studies are focused on other resources to be recovered from the water sector. In particular, Amsterdam case study aims to recover and produce new bio composite materials from the water cycle. Hamar case study has the objective to recover struvite. While Stavanger case study aims to produce upgraded biogas and organic fertiliser from WWTP sludge. For all these latter three case studies, the projection is to achieve the objective in 2024. For Hamar and Stavanger case studies, the activities have been already implemented at full-scale level. For all cases, at now it is still not possible to define precise boundaries of the effects (e.g., use or market) of the recovered resources since it often depends on the composition and properties of the resources.

Regarding the *drivers*, a great social awareness about the need to move towards more sustainable resources, materials and solutions has been observed for all case studies. Further, the current regulatory conditions (guidelines to be still published, increasing carbon fee or limits in sludge regulation to be changed) is favourable towards the transition from linear to circular economy and in implementing a market on the recovered resources from water sector. The market conditions are in advanced state only for Stavangar case study since there is a concrete interest of the Local Energy Company to buy the produced biogas. This latter is still technically possible since already exists a gas grid in the region where biogas can be pumped into. For all the other case studies only general interest on the market of the recovered resources (water, struvite or fertilizer) has still been encountered. Regarding the aspects related to the environment, the common purpose to reduce the use of natural resources has been identified for all case studies. The common *pressures* are related with regulations. In particular, a common need to a tightened control and stronger enforcement of regulations from national authorities have been emphasized, coupled with the requirement of a most interactions between policy makers and decision makers.

The observed *trends* show two key aspects closely connected each other: i. economic; ii. Investments. Specifically, from the economic point of view, all the actors (mainly owner and operators) involved in the process are strongly aware that the cost of future natural resources (carbon fossil energy, water, etc.) will be higher than now. Further, their availability will decrease; thus, arise the need of pushing towards the adoption of recovered resources in view of reducing the plants operation costs or the adoption of natural resources is common. However, in view of creating virtuous systems towards the circularity, new investments are often required (mainly in Italy and Prague).

6 Conclusions

A clear and structured roadmap approach has been presented. The roadmap structure is divided into four main steps: scoping, forecasting, backcasting, and transfer. For each step, data to be collected for implementing the roadmap have been identified and summarized in a database which was presented, in each part, in the document. The database has only been filled for the scoping section from each demonstration case study. Further, each case study has been described in order to emphasize the objective, expected impact and the ambition in a roadmapping perspective. The SCES(s) have been described coupled with challenges and development needs. The analysis of scoping data of all case studies reveals that there is great social awareness about the need to move towards more sustainable resources, materials and solutions. However, in some case, the social acceptance needs to be improved. Moreover, there is a common trend to improve and upgrade with future investments to provide a virtuous and mature circular process.

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